

ALGOFLORA OF NATURAL WATER BODIES OF SOUTHERN KYRGYZSTAN

Kh.A. Alimjanova¹, M. A. Shaiymkulova²

Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent,
Uzbekistan¹

Osh State University, Osh, Kyrgyzstan²

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Abstract. During 2019-2024, the authors conducted an algological study of natural reservoirs in Southern Kyrgyzstan. As a result of the study, the authors found 92 species of algae from the Naryn River, 76 from the Kara-darya River, 260 from the Akbura River, 139 from the Isfayramsay River, 35 from the Sokh River, 137 from the Shakhimardansay River, 46 from the Isfara River, and 60 from the Mashalankul Lake, 65 from the Aydyngkul Lake, 42 from the Kuli-kubbon Lake, 36 from the Zorkul Lake, and 30 from the Tegirmachkul Lake. In the reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan, representatives of species from the Cyanophyta, Bacillariophyta and Chlorophyta departments are noted throughout the rivers and lakes. The remaining departments Rhodophyta, Xanthophyta, Chrysophyta, Pyrrophyta, Euglenophyta, Charophyta have a small number of species in river systems. And in lakes, there are no algae from four departments - Rhodophyta, Xanthophyta, Chrysophyta, Pyrrophyta. As a result of the inventory of algae flora in these reservoirs, it was revealed that the most species-rich reservoir is the Akbuura River (260), followed by Isfayramsay (139), Shakhimardansay (137). The remaining rivers and lakes have a poorer number of algae species. Frequency of occurrence of population of most species of algae is observed 1-3 points. In a small number of species and their population reaches 5, in rare cases some of them reach 7 and 9 points. Many species at this time are found in single quantities, that is, 1 point. They are on the verge of extinction. In this regard, it is necessary to develop further protective measures for the survival of these algae, and it is also necessary to conduct a study on periodic inventory of the presence and condition of algae in natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan, at least every 10 years.

Keywords: inventory, list of algae, algal flora, species diversity, frequency of occurrence, natural, water bodies, southern, Kyrgyzstan.

Introduction

Relevance of the topic. Currently, the climate is changing and global warming is occurring all over the world. In connection with this, the northern and southern poles and high-mountainous parts of the Earth experience premature melting of ice and a reduction in the area of ice reserves at the poles and ice tongues on the mountains is observed. These natural phenomena affect other objects, such as natural reservoirs, low river water levels, low water levels in lakes and groundwater.

Water is life for all existing organisms on Earth, including biologically valuable objects for algae, which are a source of oxygen for breathing, vitamin-rich protein food reserves for aquatic organisms, which play a major role in the natural food web. In this regard, it is necessary to conduct a periodic inventory and study the species composition of algae in natural reservoirs of Kyrgyzstan,

including its southern part, which is a mountain water body and the main source of the river supplying water to the republics of Central Asia, such as the Syr Darya and its tributaries - Akbuura, Naryn, Kara Darya, Isfayramsay, Sokh, Shakhimardansay, Isfara and some others. In this regard, this topic is very relevant. In this regard, we conducted algological studies on the reservoirs of rivers and lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan during 2019-2024.

The aim of the research topic is to conduct an inventory and study the species composition of the algal flora of natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan in conditions of climate change and their consequences.

The objectives of the study are: 1) To determine monitoring points for sampling in the studied objects, such as rivers and lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan; 2). To determine the species composition of algal flora of the river and lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan and to compile a list of algae for each separately; 3). To analyze the floristic composition of water bodies in Southern Kyrgyzstan.

The objects of the study are the algal flora of the river and lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan: from the river - Naryn, Kara-darya, Akburra, Isfayramsay, Sokh, Shakhimardansay, Isfara; from the lakes - Zorkul, Tegirmachkul, Kuli-kubbon, Mashalankul and Aydynkul. Monitoring points for seasonal sampling of algae and for measuring water and air temperature, transparency and pH of water, mineralization, flow rate and other indicators have been identified.

To achieve the goal and objectives of this topic, we used a number of research methods.

Materials and Methods. To collect algological samples from the river and lakes, we used the "Methods of collecting and studying algae" given in the book Identifier of freshwater algae of the USSR. Issue 1. General part. Freshwater algae and their study, written by the author algologists Gollerbakha M.M. and Polyansky V.I. (Moscow, 1951) [1].

As a result of the field research, we collected and processed more than 350 algological samples: phytoplankton, phytobenthos and periphyton. The species composition was determined using the USSR freshwater algae guides, issues 2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10,11,13,14 [2-12] and the guides to blue-green and protococcal algae of Central Asia [13-15], and some monographs were also used [16-17]. When determining the frequency of occurrence in three algae size categories, a frequency scale of 1-9 was used [18].

Results and Discussion. During 2019-2024, we conducted an algological study of natural reservoirs in Southern Kyrgyzstan. Monitoring stations were noted from the rivers - Naryn, Kara-darya, Akburra, Isfayramsay, Sokh, Isfara, Shakhimardansay, as well as from the lakes Zorkul, Tegirmachkul, Kuli-kubbon, Mashalankul and Aydynkul. More than 350 algological samples were collected and processed.

The samples were processed, temporary and permanent preparations were prepared, then a study was conducted under a microscope and the species composition of the algae of the objects under study was determined. As a result of the study, the species composition was determined and a flora-taxonomic list of algae of the rivers and lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan was compiled.

Analysis of algal flora of the rivers of Southern Kyrgyzstan. Analysis of the floristic composition of algae of Southern Kyrgyzstan gave the following results: during the study period we found from the studied monitoring stations of the studied objects, such as from the Naryn River 92 species of algae, from the Kara-Darya River - 76, the Akbuura River - 260, the Isfayramsay River - 139, the Sokh River - 35, the Shakhimardansay River - 137, the Isfara River - 46 species of algae (table 1).

Table 1. Number of algae species in the rivers of the Southern Kyrgyzstan basin

No.	Name of the division of algae	Naryn	Karadar ya	Akbuura	Isfayram-say	Shakhimardansay	Sokh	Isfara
1.	<i>Cyanophyta</i>	14	12	45	21	12	2	22
2.	<i>Rhodophyta</i>	-	-	1	3	2	-	3
3.	<i>Xanthophyta</i>	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
4.	<i>Chrysophyta</i>	-	-	1	1	1	1	1
5.	<i>Bacillariophyta</i>	54	42	147	105	117	26	10
6.	<i>Pyrrophyta</i>	-	-	3	-	-	-	-
7.	<i>Euglenophyta</i>	-	-	5	-	-	-	-
8.	<i>Chlorophyta</i>	24	22	56	9	5	6	10
9.	<i>Charophyta</i>	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
	Total :	92	76	260	139	137	35	46

From the tables 1 it is evident that the richest departments in terms of species biodiversity are Bacillariophyta, which are listed in the algal flora of the Akbuura River – 147, Shakhimardansay– 117, Isfayramsay – 105 species of algae. In other rivers, the species composition of diatoms is 54 in the Naryn River, 42 in the Kara-Darya River, 26 in the Sokh River, and 10 species of algae in the Isfara River. Diatom species of algae in these reservoirs are found in most cases singly or rarely (occurrence - 1 or 3 points). In some cases in the Akbuura River some species of diatom algae are found frequently (occurrence is equal to 5 points). For example, *Diatoma hiemale* (Lingb.) Hust., *Cratoneis arcus* var. *amphioxys* (Rabenh.) Brun., *Achnanthes affinis* Grun., *Pinularia intermedia* f. *minor* Boye P., *Cymbella sinuate* Greg., *C.skvortzowii* Skabitch., *C.tartuensis* Molder. In a single case, *Diatoma vulgare* var. *productum* Grun is very often found in the Akbuura River, its frequency of occurrence is equal to seven points. The remaining species of diatoms in the Akbuura River are found singly or rarely. This probably depends on the poor mineral substances and low temperatures of mountain water environments and the biological cold-loving and oligotrophic features of some of the major algae in the studied reservoirs.

After diatoms, *Chlorophyta* comes second in terms of species diversity of algae. According to species richness in the algal flora of the river, Akbuura is richer with green algae than other algal flora of the rivers. In the Akbuura river, 56 species of green algae are noted. Then, in the Naryn river - 24, in the Kara-darya river - 22, in Isfara - 10, Isfayramsay - 9, Sokh - 6, Shakhimardansay - 5. In all water bodies, the occurrence under the microscope in a certain area of the Goryaeva Chamber, green algae are noted singularly and rarely. A single case is observed in the Akbuura River, some species are found frequently. For example: *Pediastrum duplex* Meyen, *Crucigenia rectangulatum* (A.Dr.) Gay, *Actinastrum hantzschii* Lagerh., *Cosmarium subcrenatum* Hantzsch. Some species are rare and common, such as *Scenedesmus obliquus* var. *alternans* Christjuk., *Ulothrix tenerrima* Kuetz., *U.tenuissima* Kuetz., *U.zonata* Kuetz. In a single case, rare and mass occurrences (on a three- and nine-point scale) were observed, such as *Scenedesmus obliquus* (Turp.) Kuetzing.

In terms of species richness, *Cyanophyta* ranks third. Here, too, the Akbuura River is richer in species composition of biodiversity. There are 45 species of algae. The rest of the rivers have

poorer blue-green algae. There are 22 species of algae in the Isfara River, then the Isfayramsay River - 21, Kara-Darya - 12, and only 2 species of blue-green algae were found in the Sokh River. The species composition and biodiversity of other departments are poorer. For example, species of red algae – *Rhodophyta* in the Akbuura River are rarely noted and often the only species is *Bangia atropurpurea* (Roth.)Ag. In Isfayramsay, 3 species were noted: single and rare - *Bangia atropurpurea* (Roth.) Ag., single and very rare - *Lemania fluviatilis* Ag., very rare - *Batrachospermum moniliforme* Roth.). In Shakhimardansay, 2 species were noted single and very rare - *Bangia atropurpurea* (Roth.) Ag. and single - *Batrachospermum moniliforme* Roth. In the Isfara River, three species of red algae have been noted: *Bangia atropurpurea* (Roth.) Ag. – single and rare, *Lemania fluviatilis* Ag. – single and very rare, *Batrachospermum moniliforme* Roth. – very rare.

Xanthophyta is noted only in the Akbuura River, only one species - rarely found *Characiopsis borziana* Lemm.

Chrysophyta is also found rarely and often *Hydrurus faetidus* Kirchner in the Akbuura River, singly - in Isfayramsay, very rarely and rarely - in Shokhimardansay, very rarely - in the Sokh River and singly noted in the Isfara River.

Pyrrophyta are noted only in the Akbuura River, such as the rare *Peridinium cinktum* (O.F.M.) Ehr., *P.palatinum* Laut., *P.umdonatum* Stein. and the single and frequently observed *Ceratium hirundinella* (O.F.M.) Berg.

Euglenophyta are noted only in the Akbuura River, 5 species - such as the rare and common *Euglena brevis* P.Christ., often - *E.buharica* Kissel., *E.proxima* Dang., *E.oxuyris* Schmarada, *E.hemichromata* Skuja.

Charaphyta are also noted only in the Akbuura River, such as the common and abundant *Chara vulgaris* var.*crassiculis* Kuetz.

Algae are spread in more than one form along the rivers. Among the rivers rich in species biodiversity of algae is the Akbuura River (260 species), then Isfayramsay (139), Shakhimardansay (137), in the rest of the rivers the species composition of algae is noticeably low.

Analysis of algal flora of lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan. Floristic analysis of lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan gave us the following results, that is, during the study period we found from lakes Mashalankul - 60, Aydynkul - 65, Kuli-kubbon - 42, Zorkul - 36, Tegirmachkul - 30 species of algae (Table 2).

Table 2. Number of algae species in lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan

No.	Name of the division of algae	Mashalankul	Aydynkul	Kuli-kubbon	Zorkul	Tegirmachkul
1.	<i>Cyanophyta</i>	5	12	13	4	5
2.	<i>Rhodophyta</i>	-	-	-	-	-
3.	<i>Xanthophyta</i>	-	-	-	-	-
4.	<i>Chrysophyta</i>	-	-	-	-	-
5.	<i>Bacillariophyta</i>	47	39	25	26	15
6.	<i>Pyrrophyta</i>	-	-	-	-	-
7.	<i>Euglenophyta</i>	-	2	-	-	-
8.	<i>Chlorophyta</i>	7	21	4	3	10
9.	<i>Charophyta</i>	1	1	-	-	-

	Total :	60	56	42	36	30
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As can be seen from table 2, not a single species of the *Rhodophyta*, *Xanthophyta*, *Chrysophyta* and *Pyrrophyta* algae divisions were noted when comparing rivers. In lakes, only species of algae from the *Cyanophyta*, *Bacillariophyta*, *Chlorophyta*, *Euglenophyta* and *Charophyta* divisions were found.

Here, as in rivers, the diatom division is considered to be rich in species diversity compared to other divisions of algae. Among the lakes, Mashalankul is considered the richest, with 47 species, followed by Aydynkul (39), Zorkul (26), Kulikubbon (25) and Tegirmachkul (15). Among diatoms, *Achnanthes minutissima* Kuetz. was frequently observed in Lake Tegirmachkul. *Cymbella pusilla* Grun., *C.ventricosa* Kuetz., *Gomphonema angustatum* (Kuetz.) Rabenh., *Nitzschia dissipata* (Kuetz.) Grun., *N.hantzschiana* Rabenh. were frequently and rarely observed in Lake Mashalankul. Other species of diatoms are found in some lakes singly, very rarely, rarely, and in some cases they are absent from some lakes.

Chlorophyta ranks second in species richness after diatoms in lakes. Among the lakes, the richest in algae species is considered to be Lake Aydin-Kul, which has 21 species of green algae, followed by other lakes such as Tegirmachkul (10), Mashalan-Kul (7), Kuli-kubbon (4) and Zorkul (3). Among green algae such as *Pediastrum boryanum* (Turp.) Menegh., *P.boryanum* var. *cornutum* (Racib.) Sulek. are frequently noted, and *Oocystis gigas* Archer., *O.lacustris* Chodat. were observed rarely, very rarely in Lake Aydinkul. *Cladophora fracta* Kuetz. and *Cladophora glomerata* (I) Kuetz. are frequently noted in Lake Kulikubbon, very rarely – in Lake Zorkul.

In terms of species richness, the third place is occupied by the blue-green algae (*Cyanophyta*) department. In the Kulikubbon lakes, 13 species of algae were noted, Aydynkul - 12, Mashalankul and Tegirmachkul - 5 species each, and Zorkul - 4 species of algae. Among blue-green algae, *Merismopedia glauca* (Ehr.) Naeg. is rare and common in Lake Aydinkul and abundant in Kulikubbon. *Merismopedia punctata* Meyen. is often found in Lake Kulikubbon, and in other lakes it is rarely or singularly noted; it was not found in Tegirmachkul. Species of the genera *Gloeocapsa* (Kuetz.) Hollerb.emend. are noted singly and rarely *G.alpina* Naeg em.Brend. and *G.alpina* f. *typica* Holler. in Lake Aydinkul. They are not found in the other lakes. In Lake Kulikubbon, *G.rupestris* Kuetz. and *Nostoc paludosum* Kuetz., *N.punctiforme* Ag., *Scytonema alatum* f. *majus* Kossink are often observed. In other lakes, algae are rare or isolated, and in some cases, they are even absent.

Euglenophyta has only 2 species in Lake Aydynkul – *Euglena breves* P.Christ., *E.oxyuris* Schmarida, they are rarely noted.

Charophyta – one species is noted in Lakes Mashalankul and Aydynkul. This species is *Chara vulgare* L. and its occurrence is equal to 7 points, that is, it is found very often.

As a result of the inventory of algal flora and floristic analysis of species biodiversity and their occurrence in the natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan given above shows that in these reservoirs, it was revealed that the most species-rich reservoir is the Akbuura River (260), followed by Isfayramsay (139), Shakhimardansay (137). The remaining rivers and lakes have a poorer species composition of algae. It should be further noted that, in comparison with the algal flora of rivers, the algal flora of lakes is less rich, and in some cases the algal species of some divisions (*Rhodophyta*, *Xanthophyta*, *Chrysophyta* and *Pyrrophyta*) are almost absent. This is explained by the fact that the rivers and lakes of Southern Kyrgyzstan are high-mountain and mountain reservoirs, and therefore the temperature here is lower than the reservoirs of the flat parts of Central

Asia. In addition, the water of most reservoirs in Southern Kyrgyzstan is oligotrophic rather than mesotrophic. This means that the water contains less nutrients for the algae to live on. In this regard, cold-water and oligotrophic algae are common here, while mesotrophic and more heat-loving algae are found in the lower part of the Akbuura River. More cold-loving and oligotrophic algae are common in the lakes.

In natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan many algae are found in single quantities only in the place indicated below, and in other places they are not found at all, they are like in rivers - **from blue-green algae** - *Gloeocapsa compacta* Kuetz. (in the Akbuura River), *G.minuta* (Kuetz.) Holltrb., (in the Akbuura and Isfayramsay Rivers), *G.turgida* (Kuetz) Hollerb. (in the Akbuura, Isfayramsay and Isfara Rivers), *Eucapsis alpine* Glem.et Shantz. (in the Akbuura River); and **from diatoms** - *Melosira granulate* var. *angustissima* (O.Muell.) Hust., *Synedra tabulate* var. *parva* (Kuetz.) Grun., *Diatomella balfourina* Gray (in the Akbuura River), *D.puella* (Schum) Ceval. (in the Isfara River), *D.pusila* (Schum) Cleve (in the Isfayramsay River), *D.schmidthii* (Breb.) Cleve (in the Isfayramsay and Isfara Rivers), *Stauroneis smithii* Grun. (in the Isfayramsay, Shakhimardansay rivers), *Navicula anglica* Ralfs var. *subcruciata* Grun., *Navicula lanceolate* var. *cymbula* (Donk.) Cl., *Pinnularia appendiculata* (Ag.) Cl., *P.sublinearis* Grun. (in the Shakhimardansay river), *P.viridis* var. *sudetica* (Hilse.) Hust. (in the Isfayramsay river), *Cymbella tumida* (Breb.) V.H. (in the Akbuura river), *Gomphonema intricatum* var. *pumilum* Grun., *G.intricatum* var. *minor* Skv., *G.intricatum* var. *vibrio* (Ehr.) Cl. (in the Shakhimardansay river), *Epithemia zebra* var. *saxonica* (Kuetz.) Grun. (in the Isfayramsay and Isfara rivers), *Nitzschia angustata* (W.Sm.) Grun., *N.angustata* var. *acuta*, *N.communis* Rabh. var. *minuta* Bbleisch., *N.frustulum* var. *subsalina* Hust., *N.heufleriana* Grun., *N.obtusa* W.Sm. var. *kryophila* Cl. (in the Shakhimardansay river), *N.ovalis* var. *pinnata* W. Smith. (in the rivers Isfayramsay, Isfara), *Cymatopleura noticus* var. *hibernicus* (Ehr.) Grun. (in the Isfara River); **of the green algae**, the following were found singly: *Pediastrum muticum* Kuetz., *Oocystis crassa* Wittrock., *Scenedesmus denticulatus* Lagerheim, *S.denticulatus* var. *linearis* Hansg., *Ankistrodesmua arcuatus* Korschik., *A.braunii* (Naeg.) Collins., *A.falcatus* (Corda) Ralfs., *Closterium acerosum* (Schrank) Ehr., *Cosmarium biretum* Breb. (in the Akbuur River). *Cymbella aequalis* W.Sm. is found in lakes only occasionally (in Lake Tegirmachkul). Other species of algae are very rarely and rarely found in other lakes.

These species, which are found in single quantities, we think that they are on the verge of disappearing state. The population of these species consists of very small quantities. In this regard, it is very necessary to conduct periodic inventories of the algal flora of natural reservoirs (rivers and lakes) of Southern Kyrgyzstan.

Conclusion.

1. During the study of the species composition of the biodiversity of algae in natural reservoirs (rivers and lakes) of Southern Kyrgyzstan, we found for the first time that among these rivers, the Akbuura River (260), Isfayramsay (139), Shakhimadansay (137) are rich in species, while the remaining rivers (Naryn-92, Karadarya - 76, Isfara-46, Sokh-35) have a small population of algae species. In comparison with rivers, the biological diversity of lakes is marked by few species of algae, such as Aydynkul has 65, Mashalankul - 60, Kulikubbon - 42, Zorkul - 36, Tegirmachkul - 30 species of algae, in addition, there are no species of algae in the lakes in the *Rhodophyta*, *Xanthophyta*, *Chrysophyta* and *Pyrrophyta* divisions. This is explained by the fact that the natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan are high mountain and mountain reservoirs, the

temperature here is lower, the nutrients of the aquatic environments are poorer, in connection with this, in these territories more cold-water and oligotrophic species of algae are widespread, adapted to these environmental conditions.

2. The population abundance of each algae species was measured on a scale of 1-9 points, and the frequency of occurrence of most algae species in natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan reaches no more than 1-3 points (singly, very rarely, rarely), for some small algae species the frequency of occurrence reaches up to 5 points (often) such as *Gomphosphaeria aponia* f. *condiformis* (Wolle) Elenk., *Hapalosiphon fontinalis* (Ag.) Born.em.Elenk. (in the Akbuur River), *Scytonema alatum* f. *majus* Kosinsk. (in Lake Kulikubbon), *Pinnularia intricatum* f. *minor* Boye P., *Euglena bucharica* Kisel., *E.proxima* Dang., *Pediastrum duplex* Meuen., *Crucigenia rectangularis* (A.Br.) Gay., *Actinastrum hantzschii* Lagerh., (in the Akbuury River), *Closterium ralfsii* var. *gubridum*, *Cl.venus* Kuetz. (in Lake Aydynkul), *Cosmarium subcrenatum* Hantzsch. (in the Akbuury River), in rare cases some species of algae reach up to 7 points (very often), such as *Diatoma vulgare* var. *productum* Grun. (in the Sokh River) and 9 points (mass), such as *Merismopedia punctate* Meyen (in Lake Kulikubbon).

3. Most species of algae of natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan and their populations are found only in single quantities in certain measured areas, especially in river systems, such as blue-green algae - *Gloeocapsa compacta* Kuetz., *G.minuta* (Kuetz.) Holltrb., *G.turgida* (Kuetz) Hollerb., *Eucapsis alpine* Glem.et Shantz. and others; of diatoms - *Melosira granulate* var. *angustissima* (O.Muell.) Hust., *Synedra tabulate* var. *parva* (Kuetz.) Grun., *Diatomella balfourina* Gray (in the Akbuure River), *D.puella* (Schum) Ceval. and others; of green algae, single specimens of *Pediastrum muticum* Kuetz., *Oocystis crassa* Wittrock., *Scenedesmus denticulatus* Lagerheimю and others have been recorded. The state of these species, we believe, is that they are on the verge of extinction. In this regard, in the future it is necessary to develop protection measures for small populations of algae species of natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan.

4. Periodically conduct inventory studies on the state of species diversity of natural reservoirs of Southern Kyrgyzstan, at least every 10 years.

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